

Social Networking Sites (SNS) Usage Behaviour Among College Students

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Abstract

Social Networking Sites (SNS) are termed as web based services which gives a chance to individuals to build their own personal summary and thereby connect with others in an overall public forum which provides them with features like chatting, blogging, video calling, mobile connectivity and video/photo sharing. Today's technology state in rapid growth, speed in browsing and connectivity with technology has made the greatest invention of social media or social networking. Youth has transformed their needs of recognitions, knowledge sharing, friendships, all in one compact pack of this social sites/social media. Social networking sites has become part of youth's life in variety of forms, by considering that today's culture is oriented by technology. Maximum of the time social networking sites are used to converse with people who are already their known or friends or relatives or connections in the social network sharing same mindset or interests, views discussions, discussions on debatable topics, news articles, latest updates on fashion or gadgets are the most common topics on these social media channels. This article analyse the college students behaviour towards various social media networking sites and their priorities towards social media.

Key words: Social media, networking, internet, Facebook, Youtube

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media is most recent form of media and having many features and characteristics. It has many facilities on same channel like as communicating, texting, audio and video sharing and linking with all over world. Its use is increasing step by step with far above the ground rate in all over the world. People waste more than usual hours on social networking sites to download pictures, browse through updates seek entertainment and chat around with friends to keep themselves associated to one another. Today the Internet has taken a firm place in people's lives. The modern reality requires us to stay in touch and keep alongside each other of the latest news and trends. Due to the rapid attractiveness of social networking sites the students tends to distract themselves from their studies and professions but on the contrary is also developing friendly and social ties with the world that revolves around them. Students are among the most prolific users of social network sites (SNS). Emerging studies find that students spend a considerable portion of their daily life interacting through social media. Subsequently, questions and controversies emerge on the effects of SNS. Social media can be described as the use of web-based and mobile technology to convert communications into an

interactive dialogue. Interactive or electronic communication is a form of indirect communication, because communicating parties are not “face-to-face.” Social media networks serve not only as a platform to socialise with friends and family, but also play a major role in the effective promotion of business. Some prominent social Medias are facebook, twitter, google+, Wikipedia, linkedin, Flickr, Instagram and Quora.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Amin, Z (2016) found out that academic outcome of students who spent most of their time interact using social media are positive because they were able to share and create ideas and concepts related to their studies. In another study of Owusu-Acheaw & Larson (2015), discovered that the use of social media had affected the academic performance of their respondents negatively and further recognized that there was a tough positive connection between the use of social media and academic performance. Their study further exposed that most of their respondents use social media sites to chat rather than for academic purpose. Andres Kaplan (2010) describe in a study stating that social media is a set of internet based function that constructs on the technological foundation which connect and permit the design and replace of user generated content. Shrestha lucky (2013), describe that social media is means of links among people in which they create, share, and exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and networks. Bryer and Zavatarro (2011), social media is “the technologies that facilitate social interaction, make possible collaboration, and enable deliberations across stakeholders”. Going by this definition, social media includes such tools as electronic blogs, audio/video tools like YouTube, internet and chat rooms, cellular and computer texting, and social networking sites (SNSs).

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To understand the usage behavior of social networking sites by the college students
2. To judge the preferred outline of social media networking sites for students.
3. To know the attitude of students towards social media and appraise the spending time.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

In this study the researcher identified how social networking sites influence the students and it would able to give why students use smart phones, and also can identify which is the popular networking site among the students. The researcher conducted the study during October to December 2019, and the data were collected from the under graduate arts and science students from Cuddalore districts and the number of samples limited to 100, since the sample size is small the result of this study cannot be universal.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study deals with a survey on the usage behavior of the social media networking in the field of college students. The social media which is used in the research tool are Face book, Skype, Quora, Twitter, Google+, LinkedIn, Instagram, Flickr, WhatsApp and YouTube. The study is based primarily on field data. To carry out the study 100 respondents who were using mobile phones were contacted. Those who were willing to provide with the necessary details

were selected for the study. The needed data were collected through structural interview schedule with administered to 100 respondents who were using Smartphone and studying in Arts and Science colleges. All the participants responded to the questionnaire. The qualification of the respondents is under graduate arts and science students studying in government and private colleges in cuddalore districts in Tamilnadu. Majority of the respondents belong to rural areas. The average age groups which are being contacted by this researcher were between 18-22 years.

A. Collection of Primary Data

For the purpose of the present study, the necessary Primary data have been collected using a survey method with the help of a prearranged questionnaire administered in person from the respondents. The researcher has totally collected 100 responses for the present study. Hence, the sample of 100 is considered for this study and a total of 100 responses were obtained between the period of October and December 2019.

B. Collection of Secondary Data

The researcher collected secondary data on Smartphone has been collected from Journals, Magazines, Reports and company's News Bulletin and Internet sources.

C. Statistical Tools Used

First hand information is collected from 100 respondents. Responses were coded and data entered and then analysed using a Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) statistics 20.0 to get inferences. Descriptive analysis were used to describe the sample, to show the numbers and percentage of items into categories, percentage analysis, Pearson Chi-Square test, and ranking method were used for this study.

6. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study limited to 100 Arts and science under graduate students who is studying in Government and private Arts and science college in Cuddalore district in Tamilnadu. The study results cannot be generalized as the number of samples is small.

Data Analysis and Results

Percentage analysis, Pearson Chi-Square test, Ranking method were used for this study. Data were analysed using SPSS software package 20.0.

7. RESULTS

Table – 1 Profile of the Respondents

Factors		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	37	37.0	37.0
	Female	63	63.0	100.0
Type of family	Nuclear Family	12	12.0	12.0
	Joint Family	88	88.0	100.0
Marital Status	Married	14	14.0	14.0
	Unmarried	86	86.0	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Totally 100 respondents were considered for this study. Among the respondents 37% of the respondents were male and 63% of respondents were female. Regarding the type of family 12% of the respondents belongs to nuclear family and rest of the 88% of the respondents belongs to joint family. And from the data it is identified that 14% of the respondents were married respondents and 86% of them were unmarried. From the data it is observed that most of the respondents were female and most of the respondents come from joint family and unmarried.

Table – 2 Purpose of Smartphone usage

GENDER												
Purpose of Smartphone Cross tabulation												
			Purpose									Total
			Phone Calls	Browsing	Email	Shopping	Travel Planner	Social Media	News	Music	Picture	
Gender	Male	Count	33	19	12	10	5	17	12	20	13	37
		% within Gender	89.2 %	51.4 %	32.4 %	27.0 %	13.5 %	45.9 %	32.4 %	54.1 %	35.1 %	
		% of Total	33.0 %	19.0 %	12.0 %	10.0 %	5.0 %	17.0 %	12.0 %	20.0 %	13.0 %	37.0 %
	Female	Count	64	9	15	7	6	46	23	49	29	63

	% within Gender	101.6 %	14.3 %	23.8 %	11.1 %	9.5 %	73.0 %	36.5 %	77.8 %	46.0 %	
	% of Total	64.0 %	9.0 %	15.0 %	7.0 %	6.0 %	46.0 %	23.0 %	49.0 %	29.0 %	63.0 %
Total	Count	97	28	27	17	11	63	35	69	42	100
	% of Total	97.0 %	28.0 %	27.0 %	17.0 %	11.0 %	63.0 %	35.0 %	69.0 %	42.0 %	100.0 %
Percentages and totals are based on respondents.											
a. Group											

Source: Primary Data

Table shows the opinion of the respondents regarding the purpose for using the Smartphone. Among the respondents 33% of the male and 64% of the female respondents used Smartphone for making calls, 17% of the male and 46% of the female respondents used Smartphone for social media. To listen music 20% of the male and 49% of the female respondents were using Smartphone. Among the respondents, 13% of the male and 29% of the female used Smartphone for taking selfie/pictures. Likewise 19% of the male and 9% of the female used Smartphone for browsing and 12% of the male and 15% of the female used the Smartphone for e-mailing.

Percentage analysis results

The result shows that 97% of the total respondents use their smart phone for phone calling, 69% of the respondents used their smart phone to listen music and 63% of them used their smart phone for social media. The respondents give less importance to shopping (17%) and travel planner (11%).

Table – 3 Number Hours used by the respondents

GENDER * HOURS OF USE Crosstabulation					
Count					
		Hours use			Total
		1-2 Hrs	2-3 Hrs	As Per Need	
Gender	Male	3	8	26	37
	Female	12	10	41	63
Total		15	18	67	100

Source: Primary Data

Table represents the number of hours the respondents used their Smartphone per day. Among the respondents, 15% of them (male 3%) and (female 12%) used their Smartphone at minimum of 1-2 hours per day, 18% of the respondents (male 8%) and (female 10%) used

their Smart phone for 2-3 hours per day and 67% of the respondents (male 26%) and (female 41%) used their Smart phone as per the need.

Chi-Square Tests Results

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.381 ^a	2	0.304
Likelihood Ratio	2.554	2	0.279
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.093	1	0.296
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.55.

Chi-Square test results

Chi-Square test result shows that 67% of the respondents used their Smartphone as per their needs without any time limit and from the Pearson chi-square test result show that there is no significant variation among the gender regarding the usage of Smartphone and hours of usage of the Smartphone.

Table – 4 WhatsApp usage Behaviour

Crosstab				
Count				
		WhatsApp		Total
		Several Time a Day	Some times a Day	
Gender	Male	24	13	37
	Female	27	36	63
Total		51	49	100

Source: Primary Data

Table shows the whatsapp usage behavior among the respondents, from the analysis it is observed that 51% of the respondents used their Smartphone (male 24%) and (female 27%) respondents used the Smartphone phone several time a day for WhatsApp and 49% of the respondents (male 13%) and (female 36%) used Smartphone sometimes a day. It is observed that most of the respondents spent more time on WhatsApp.

Chi-Square Tests Results					
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.518 ^a	1	0.034		
Continuity Correction ^b	3.680	1	0.055		
Likelihood Ratio	4.570	1	0.033		
Fisher's Exact Test				0.040	0.027
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.473	1	0.034		
N of Valid Cases	100				
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 18.13.					
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table					

Pearson Chi-Square test results

From the Pearson Chi-Square test, it is observed that among the male and female respondents using the WhatsApp there is a significant difference is observed (Chi-square value = 4.518) and p – value is .034.

Table – 5 You Tube usage Behaviour

Crosstab					
Count					
		YouTube			Total
		Several Time a Day	Some times a Day	Once in a week	
Gender	Male	20	17	0	37
	Female	33	28	2	63
Total		53	45	2	100

Source: Primary Data

Table shows the respondents You Tube usage behavior, among the 53% respondents (male 20%) and (female 33%) used their Smartphone for watching You Tube channels several time a day and 45% of the respondents (male 17%)and (female 28%) watching the You Tube channels nearly every day and less number of respondents (2%) watching You Tube channels once in a week, from the analysis It is noted that the respondents used the You Tube channels more often.

Chi-Square Tests Results			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.199 ^a	2	0.549
Likelihood Ratio	1.872	2	0.392
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.187	1	0.665
N of Valid Cases	100		
a. 2 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .74.			

Pearson Chi-Square test results

Pearson Chi-Square test shows that among the male and female respondents in using You Tube, there is no significant difference of opinion in using You Tube among the male and female respondents.

Table – 6 Ranking Analysis & Results

Preference of Social Media	Response Level on Preference of Social media									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Google +	16	9	18	29	12	11	2	2	1	
Linkedin	4			2	2	14	23	23	18	14
Facebook	2	22	36	18	8	3	3	4	3	1
Twitter		3	9	8	19	20	23	5	6	7
YouTube	13	28	21	13	16	3	1	3	2	
Instagram	4	9	9	10	16	22	7	13	8	2
Flickr	1			4	14	8	17	29	20	7
Snapchat	6	3	1	13	7	12	15	16	18	9
WhatsApp	54	25	4	3	4	1	1	2	4	2
Quora	2	2	1		2	6	8	5	19	55

Source: Primary Data

Ranking results

Table shows respondents opinion towards the preferred social media networking sites. Respondents were asked to express their opinion and rank the various social media networking sites, and they ranked them. According to the data 54% of the respondents used WhatsApp and they ranked first, 28% of the respondents used YouTube and ranked second. And Facebook had the respondent's level of 36% followed by Google+ with 29% level and ranked third and fourth rank respectively, 19% of the respondents prefer Twitter and ranked fifth level followed by Instagram with 22% response and ranked sixth level. Respondents ranked Quora social media at the last.

8. FINDINGS

Among the respondents 37% of the respondents were male and 63% of them were female, and 12% of the respondents belongs to nuclear family and rest of the 88% of them were from joint family, and 14% of the respondents were married and 86 % of them were unmarried. Regarding the opinion of the respondents about use of Smartphone 33% of the male and 64% of the female respondents used Smartphone for making calls, 17% of the male and 46% of the female respondents used Smartphone for social medial. So it is noted that most of the respondents using smart phone for making calls. The respondents used their smart phone for social media and followed by taking pictures or selfie and browsing, e-mails. Among the respondents 67% of them used their Smartphone as per their requirement irrespective of the

gender. Among the respondents 51% of them used their Smartphone several times a day for WhatsApp social media and also there is a considerable difference among male and female. In case of usage of You Tube social media, 53% of the respondents used their Smartphone several times a day and there is no difference of opinion on usage behavior among the gender. Most preferred social media ranked first among the students is WhatsApp followed by other social media such as You Tube, Facebook, Google+, Twitter, Instagram/Linkedin, Flickr and Quara.

9. CONCLUSION

Most of the students generally used their smart phone for phone calls, when they used it for social media networking sites; they use mostly WhatsApp, You Tube and Facebook etc. student's positive attitude towards social media can help the student academic career and their life style. Social media is a helpful tool for students so its use is indispensable to get information and awareness. when student going to unite with the social media they should be more careful that the basic purpose of use, and they should consider that information which they are going to share is not only for their happiness and concern but it is also for well wishers and society which they belongs. Hence they should be more careful and use with social responsibility.

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